

THE PECULIARITY OF HAMLET'S TRAGEDY IN THE WORK OF WILLIAM SHAKESPEARE

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ANNOTATION.

William Shakespeare's tragedy Hamlet was written in 1600-1601 and is one of the most famous works of world literature. The plot of the tragedy is based on the legend of the ruler of Denmark, dedicated to the story of the protagonist's revenge for the death of his father. In Hamlet, Shakespeare raises a number of important topics concerning the morality, honor and duty of the characters. The author pays special attention to the philosophical theme of life and death.

Key words: morality, spirit, quarto, disillusioned, bloodshed, swordsman, fratricide, treason.

Introduction. "Hamlet" (The Tragedy of Hamlet, Prince of Denmark) is a tragedy written by William Shakespeare between 1599 and 1602. The events of the play take place in the Kingdom of Denmark. The spirit of Hamlet's father King Hamlet urges his son to take revenge on his uncle Claudius (Claudius). Claudius kills his brother and wins the throne, and marries his brother's widow. "Hamlet" is Shakespeare's longest play, and is considered one of the most powerful and influential tragedies in English literature. The play has been retold many times, altered. "Hamlet" is one of the most popular plays in Shakespeare's lifetime, and is still one of the author's most frequently staged works today. The work has been at number one on the list of the most popular plays of the Royal Shakespeare Company and earlier theatres in Stratford-upon-Avon since 1879. The work has inspired dozens of writers, including Johann Wolfgang von Goethe, Charles Dickens, James Joyce, and Iris Murdoch, and is described as being the most screened story after "Cinderella". Works about characters who retaliate for the death of their father, such as those in "Hamlet", appear in many works written before Shakespearean, including The Legend of Amleth. The legend is preserved in the 13th-century "Gesta Danorum" by Saxo Grammaticus, which the 16th-century scholar François de Belleforest retold. Shakespeare may have relied on a work written in the time of Elizabeth I, now known as "Hamlet", but some

researchers believe that "Hamlet" was also written by Shakespeare himself, which brought it to a form known to us later. Shakespeare wrote the title character in an adaptation for Richard Burbage, who was considered one of the best actors at the time. In the past 400 years since the play was written, Hamlet has been portrayed by several successful actors.

The first three versions of the work survive: the first quarto (K1, 1603); the second quarto (K2, 1604); and the last quarto (K3, 1623). Each version has verses and scenes that the other does not have. The structure and characters of the play have been extensively studied. One of these is a debate that has been going on for several centuries about Hamlet's hesitation to kill his uncle. While some believe that the purpose was to prolong the play, others believe that it is an expression of complex philosophical and moral concepts related to murder, planned revenge, and faded desire. **The main characters** Hamlet– Prince of Denmark, son of the former and nephew of the current king, was killed by Laertes. Claudius, the Danish king, killed Hamlet's father and married Gertrude, was killed by Hamlet.

Polonius– the chief royal adviser, the father of Laertes and Ophelia, was killed by Hamlet. Laertes– the son of Polonius, the brother of Ophelia, a skilled swordsman, was killed by Hamlet. Horatio -is a close friend of Hamlet.

Other characters Ophelia is the daughter of Polonius, the sister of Laertes, after the death of her father she went mad, drowned in the river. Gertrude– the Danish queen, Hamlet's mother, Claudius' wife, died after drinking wine poisoned by the king. The ghost of Hamlet 's father Rosencrantz and Guildenstern are former university comrades of Hamlet. Fortinbras is a Norwegian prince.

Marcellus, Bernardo – officers.

Results. Hamlet — dies after being wounded by a poisoned rapier in a duel with Laertes. Claudius is killed by Hamlet with a poisoned rapier. Horatio wanted to drink poison to die with Hamlet, but Hamlet dissuaded him and asked him to tell people the truth. Ophelia — after the death of her father by Hamlet's hand, she goes crazy, falls into the river and dies. Laertes — wounded during a duel with Hamlet with a poisoned rapier, dies. Gertrude — accidentally drinks poisoned wine from Hamlet's glass, dies. Polonius — hides behind a carpet, wanting to eavesdrop on the conversation between the queen and her son; killed with a sword, giving himself away: Hamlet pierced him through the carpet, believing that it was the king.

Conclusion. In Hamlet, using the example of the image of the Danish prince, Shakespeare portrays a personality of the new age, whose strength and weakness lie

in his morality and sharp mind. Being a philosopher and humanist by nature, Hamlet finds himself in circumstances that force him to revenge and bloodshed. This is the tragedy of the hero's position – after seeing the dark side of life, fratricide, treason, he became disillusioned with life, lost understanding of its value. Shakespeare does not give in his work a definite answer to the eternal question "To be or not to be ...", leaving it to the reader.

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